

The Transfiguration of Rights: A Proposal for Orthodoxy's Appropriation of Rights Language

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Abstract

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The article, building on very recent Orthodox political theology, especially that of Aristotle Papanikolaou and Panteleis Kalaitzidis, brings modern human rights theory into dialogue with Orthodox theology, seeking to bypass “a kind of xenophobia of the West” which has hindered previous attempts at dialogue. The approach is neither an uncritical rejection of rights language nor an unthinking embrace of it, but a careful discerning to see which aspects of human rights theory and practice are reconcilable with Orthodox theology. The author makes expansive use of this rights theory, opening it up, with help from Maximus the Confessor, beyond sociopolitical categories to include ecological questions in a cosmological context. He concludes by calling for further dialogue to more clearly demonstrate that human rights do not represent a threat to the mission of Orthodoxy in the world but a point of connection between the Church and the world.

Introduction

Orthodox reactions to human rights in the modern era have been disparate and varied, which makes it difficult to speak of a uniform stance on the issue. This mimics the uncertainty with which the Orthodox have approached the larger task of constructing a modern political theology. With the publication

in late 2012 of his book, *The Mystical as Political: Democracy and Non-Radical Orthodoxy*, Aristotle Papanikolaou has offered perhaps the most positive and theologically robust basis for the appropriation of human rights into a new Orthodox political theology. His thesis comes within a critique of what he calls “the Christian theological assault on modern liberal democracy.”¹ Framing his analysis of human rights within Orthodox conceptions of personhood, Papanikolaou argues that “based on the principle of divine-human communion [*theosis*], the Orthodox (and Christians, more generally) must unequivocally support the language of human rights, though fully realizing that such language falls short of expressing all that the human is created to be.”² There are three components to Papanikolaou’s thesis: (1) he establishes a basis for human rights in Orthodox theological anthropology; (2) he asserts the imperative of upholding human rights as part of his case for including core elements of liberal democracy within a new Orthodox political theology; and (3) he agrees with those Orthodox scholars who have detected in the concept of human rights an innate deficiency to express the fullness of human flourishing.

Having recently developed my own positive account of the relationship between Orthodox theology and rights language,³ I would like to correlate my own argument to the three components of Papanikolaou’s thesis, while recognizing key differences in each component. I am using Papanikolaou’s argument as a springboard for my own argument for two reasons: (1) his is one of the only modern attempts within the Western context to construct a comprehensive Orthodox political theology; and (2) it seems only proper given the basic similarities to place the differences in my own argument in relief to Papanikolaou’s argument. The first and most significant dif-

¹ Aristotle Papanikolaou, *The Mystical as Political: Democracy and Non-Radical Orthodoxy* (Notre Dame: University of Notre Dame, 2012), 87.

² Papanikolaou, *Mystical as Political*, 88.

³ Christopher Brenna, “Orthodox Christian Cosmology and Modern Rights Theories: A Proposal for Political Dialogue and Change,” presentation given at the 2012 annual meeting of the Orthodox Theological Society of America, Sept. 19, 2012, St. Vladimir’s Seminary, Crestwood, NY.

ference is that I base my argument for the usefulness of rights language not in Orthodox theological anthropology per se, but upon an Orthodox cosmology. The primary theological notion for Papanikolaou's political theology is *theosis*, which he terms "human-divine communion."⁴ The analogous cosmological principle for my argument is *transfiguration*, a concept given thorough treatment by modern Orthodox patriarchs and hierarchs in the context of ecological theology. Because this construes a more extensive foundation for rights, it allows for the justification of more than just human rights, including animal and environmental rights, as well as the rights of future generations. Secondly, my argument will lack the connection to liberal democracy as a political system that Papanikolaou's argument has. I do not share Papanikolaou's assessment of liberal democracy as the most salubrious political system with which Orthodoxy ought to be united.⁵ We agree that rights language is beneficial but not crucial. That is, it is only as beneficial within the current cultural milieu as it remains culturally relevant. Though the theological basis for employing rights is indispensable to Orthodoxy, rights language itself is dispensable, since it is only useful insofar as the cultures within which it is employed remain tractable to it.⁶ Lastly, I contend that most Orthodox scholars have mischaracterized the usefulness of rights language within the schema of Orthodox political theology.⁷ Rights language, so the argument goes, inherently recognizes human failure and is therefore inadequate to the task of relating God and humans properly. This has been the primary reason that most Orthodox scholars have ultimately portrayed rights language as detrimental to the aims of Orthodoxy. Papanikolaou, however, recognizes that despite the

⁴ Papanikolaou, *Mystical as Political*, 2.

⁵ It is not that I am opposed to Papanikolaou's assertion. I simply don't make it or an analogous assertion in my argument here. My point will be, precisely, that rights language doesn't necessarily have to employ the tenets of liberal democracy.

⁶ By personal correspondence, Papanikolaou confirms that on the provisional usefulness of rights language, we agree that it is simply, at present, the best of what's around.

⁷ See the discussion below. Among those who recognize rights as inadequate are Adamantia Pollis, Vigen Guroian, and Christos Yannaras.

fact that “political communities are necessitated in part because of sin and fear ... human rights structure relations in such a way that humans are treated as unique and irreplaceable, thus mirroring sacramental communities.”⁸ I offer a minor protest to Papanikolaou only in his concession that rights accomplish the ends of sacramental communities to a “lesser degree.” I contend that it is important to an understanding of Orthodox political theology that we recognize rights language properly employed as achieving exactly both what it is intended to do and what we need it to do within a new political theology.

My thesis, then, constructed in correlation to the three components of Papanikolaou’s thesis, is that it is *possible* (though not *necessary*) to employ the language of rights in order to establish trajectories for human flourishing intrinsic to an Orthodox transfigurational cosmology.

I have divided this study into four sections. First, I give an account of modern Orthodox reactions to rights language, answering common objections and establishing more reasonable expectations about the nature of rights language. I then explain the theological foundation for my thesis. Finally, I propose a number of concrete rights that the Orthodox could defend in American political discourse and in dialogue with the international rights community. I hope that this study will fit into the larger project of constructing a modern Orthodox political theology consonant with the realities of Western society.

Modern Orthodox Reaction to Rights

There still exists a paucity of substantive Orthodox commentary on the issue of rights from a *theological* perspective. What reactions exist are aligned in such a way that a few representative examples will suffice to advance my own argument. My purpose here is both to highlight examples of positive reception of rights by the Orthodox and to challenge

⁸ Papanikolaou, *Mystical as Political*, 130.

some of the historical and philosophical presuppositions common to several critiques of rights.⁹

Stanley Harakas and Anatasios Yannoulatos have both offered positive assessments of the relationship between human rights and Orthodoxy. Harakas assesses human rights as a positive force in the modern world with which Orthodoxy can legitimately interface. He gives numerous examples of legitimate human rights, including freedom of religion and the right to life.¹⁰ He notes that in the twentieth century, the Orthodox welcomed the passage of the United Nations Universal Declaration on Human Rights in 1948.¹¹ Numerous statements were issued in the 1980s by the Greek and Antiochian archdioceses of America and by the Orthodox Church in America protesting the violation of human rights across the world.¹² Harakas is ultimately optimistic about the ability to endorse even these secular iterations of human rights without compromising the integrity of the Orthodox Church's mission.

Like Papanikolaou, he establishes the foundation for human rights in a proper theological anthropology: all humans are created good, according to the image and likeness of God. The natural moral law present in all humans is the basis for moral duty, and rights are the expression of this moral law stated in reverse. For example, "Do not murder" establishes the right to life, "do not commit adultery" establishes the right to a stable marriage, etc. Harakas draws on the idea of classical natural law to develop the right to fair and equitable treatment

⁹ Papanikolaou provides a survey in *The Mystical as Political* of the modern Orthodox scholarship on human rights. He focuses on a number of sources that I have chosen for the most part to disregard in the interest of including representative views. However, the views of Christos Yannaras and of the Russian Orthodox Church, with which Papanikolaou treats, are contained in his critique: *Mystical as Political*, 88–98. The view of inalienable rights expressed in the document published by the Russian Orthodox Church ("Foundations of the Social Doctrine of the Russian Orthodox Church") is cursory and does not add significantly to the discussion here.

¹⁰ Stanley Harakas, "Human Rights: An Eastern Orthodox Perspective," *Journal of Ecumenical Studies* 19 (1982): 17.

¹¹ The Standing Conference of Orthodox Bishops in the Americas, for example, issued a statement in December, 1978 in support of it. Harakas, "Human Rights," 21.

¹² Harakas, "Human Rights," 21–22.

for all humans. A common human nature establishes this equality and from it are derived all other human rights.¹³

Even though Harakas acknowledges the legitimacy of justifying rights from scriptural and patristic sources,¹⁴ he notes that human rights were never addressed in the early Christian tradition in such a fashion as they are now. The accent in the Christian tradition has not been so much on claiming one's own rights, but on defending the rights of the weak and defenseless. Love may on occasion require the abandonment of one's personal rights and forgiveness may lead to allowing one's rights to be violated.¹⁵ Most importantly, rights are inextricably linked to duties. There is no right without a corresponding duty: "Wherever there is a duty there is a reciprocal right.... Accordingly, 'right' is the legal and ethical demand of the person who fulfills his duties towards others that others reciprocally fulfill their duties toward him."¹⁶ These qualifications lead Harakas to construe rights as opposed in some ways to the aims of Christian love, and thus, an ethical declension.

Anastasios Yannoulatos also displays a similar optimism that Orthodoxy *does* contain the resources to uphold rights:

Orthodox tradition in particular offers a possibility for gaining a deeper insight into the matter of human rights; it points the way to what is required if human rights are not to remain confined to dry legal docu-

¹³ Harakas, "Human Rights," 18–19. The idea that rights and duties are simply opposite sides of a coin falls apart logically. One may have a duty to something without the object of one's duty thus having a right. Nicholas Wolterstorff has pointed out that violation of a duty creates guilt, while violation of a right produces the condition of having been wronged. These are two different moral conditions that both need recognition in a system of justice. *Justice: Rights and Wrongs* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2008), 7–9, 243–44, chs. 11–12.

¹⁴ For example, the entry in the *Religious and Ethical Encyclopedia* for "The Rights of Human Beings" traces Scriptural and Traditional sources through history up to the U.N. Declaration on Human Rights. Harakas, "Human Rights," 20–21, quoting *Threskevtike kai Ethike Engkyklopaideia* (Athens: Athan Martinos Publishers, 1964), IV: 1218–1221.

¹⁵ Harakas, "Human Rights," 14.

¹⁶ Harakas, "Human Rights," 14, quoting Panagiotes Demetropoulos, *Orthodoxos Christianike Ethike* (privately published, Athens, 1970), 112.

ments; it contributes to a broadening of the scope of human rights to include those of greater depth and significance, such as the right to search for, and to find, one's true nature, one's origin and one's destination.¹⁷

Yannoulatos contributes three key ideas to the conversation. First, he stresses that it is Orthodoxy that must provide the resources to interpret human rights legislation *theologically*. Second, this interpretive task will not only give life to otherwise inert documents, but will yield new substantiations of rights, which can be embodied in legislation. Thirdly, he collapses the dichotomy established by Christos Yannaras¹⁸ and Harakas between the human quest after the divine purpose and the language of rights, contending that it *is* an established right for all humanity. He upholds the basis of rights in the theological anthropology found in Harakas' argument. Being made in the image of God defines our freedom and equality before God and is the suitable basis for affirming human rights. But Yannoulatos cautions against ascribing worth to human rights legislation *prima facie*, since wicked people will always find ways of violating human rights. Any law is simply the definition of a transgression; it holds no power in itself to be enforced justly. By a slightly different path, Yannoulatos is led to a caveat stated similarly to Harakas': the call to be truly human far exceeds the vision offered by human rights theories because it can often involve disregarding or even giving up one's own rights.¹⁹

Following these two positive appraisals, Adamantia Pollis and Vigen Guroian both offered more critical evaluations. Pollis portrayed Orthodox theology as inherently incompatible with modern human rights articulations. In her 1993 article, she asserts that because of "the centrality of mysticism, the contemplative life, and the absence of individualization in Orthodoxy," it lacks the proper foundation for upholding

¹⁷ Anastasios Yannoulatos, "Eastern Orthodoxy and Human Rights," *International Review of Mission* 73 (1984): 454.

¹⁸ See *Mystical as Political*, 89–92 for an exposition of Yannaras' argument.

¹⁹ Yannoulatos, "Eastern Orthodoxy," 463–64.

rights.²⁰ She assumes that modern individual human rights were a product of the Enlightenment, the rise of the secular state and the creation of the autonomous individual. Orthodoxy's almost entirely future eschatology "negates the importance of 'man on earth' except as a test of virtue and morality leading to the attainment of Godliness."²¹ We have only one "right" in Orthodoxy: to avoid sin and pursue virtue.

Because Pollis grounds modern rights talk almost solely in the natural rights philosophy exemplified by Locke, she must reject outright the American rights project. When she asserts that prior to the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries there *was* no secular notion of individual human rights, she implies that, since that time, no significant rival has arisen to combat this powerful new strain. Absent when the Western philosophical tradition was formed, Orthodoxy is unable to support the idea of rights. Pollis' critique is descriptive: there is simply an incongruence between Orthodox theology and modern rights theory. She leaves it to some "outstanding Orthodox theologian ... to revitalize Orthodox thought in a manner relevant to contemporary ethics."²² Given the dire tenor of her assessment, it is surprising that Pollis ends her article with such a hopeful statement.

For Vigen Guroian, "Orthodox Christology and anthropology do not support theories of autonomous and secular human rights such as those that have emerged even within Western Christian thought."²³ In the concept of human rights, humanity gains a level of autonomy that is inconsistent with the Incarnation. Although sympathetic to the basic sensibility that modern liberals seek to uphold in championing rights, Guroian is dubious of their assertion that rights represent the best hope for humanity. The tainted philosophical foundation of rights and the practical challenge of implementing them are too great.

²⁰ Adamantia Pollis, "Eastern Orthodoxy and Human Rights," *Human Rights Quarterly* 15 (1993): 343. See also her 1987 article "The State, the Law, and Human Rights in Modern Greece," *Human Rights Quarterly* 9 (1987): 587–614.

²¹ Pollis, "Eastern Orthodoxy," 341.

²² Pollis, "Eastern Orthodoxy," 353.

²³ Vigen Guroian, "Human Rights and Modern Western Faith: An Orthodox Christian Assessment," *Journal of Religious Ethics* 26 (1998): 243.

The modern nation-state is essentially atheistic and must therefore distort all its own tenets, including the use of rights, away from the Christian tradition. It would have religious people subordinate their own religious convictions to positive law and reason:

The denial of God permits the affirmation of humanity. Religious persons who think that this still leaves enough room for a common ground may be fooling themselves, perhaps not in the practical present, but almost certainly in the faithless future.²⁴

Despite this grim prediction, Guroian acknowledges that the Christian faith made possible the human rights movement, that Christians have appropriated rights language successfully in many cases, and that religious people can find some value in human rights. Human rights documents explicate the real needs and advantages of human flourishing and explain duties and responsibilities that have been revealed over the course of human social history. Though this is an approximate kind of justice, it has some value. What always demonstrates more value for Guroian, however, is the exposition of the gospel, which establishes justice in a way that rights language could never do. True repentance must “fill the brittle shell of this ethical and legal formalism” or else human selfishness will warp legitimate rights-claims.²⁵

Present in each of these assessments of rights is at least one of two common elements: (1) a valuation of rights language as a digression from the task of Christian ethical living and/or (2) a depiction of the historical and philosophical underpinnings of rights language that portrays rights as an atheistic tool developed to undermine Christian theological anthropology and to promote a competing anthropology of the radically autonomous individual. In the following section, I make the case that both of these claims are inaccurate.

²⁴ Guroian, “Human Rights,” 306.

²⁵ Guroian, “Human Rights,” 247.

The Nature of Rights

Papanikolaou is, to my knowledge, the first Orthodox scholar to challenge the assertion that human rights discourse is inherently atheistic, both on the historical and philosophical level.²⁶ The historical argument has been debunked by Brian Tierney in his 1997 book *The Idea of Natural Rights*. Tierney challenges the regurgitated historical narrative of a sudden Enlightenment shift from a classical view grounding rights in the relationship between persons to a modern subjective right.²⁷ It is not true, for example, that William of Ockham created a new semantic language for talking about rights. There existed already in the thought of Ockham's predecessors the building blocks for a discussion of rights as subjective. Rights language existed long before the Enlightenment in the appropriation that canon lawyers made of Roman law.²⁸ Papanikolaou draws on this aspect of Tierney's argument and adds that John McGuckin and Nicholas Wolterstorff have also challenged aspects of this inaccurate picture.²⁹ When this inaccuracy is removed, it frees us to understand rights language.

Many disparate philosophies have been used to justify rights. Medieval Catholic canon lawyers, Enlightenment humanists, church fathers like John Chrysostom, modern Protestant and Catholic theologians, ancient as well as modern philosophers have all successfully appropriated rights language, often without even deploying their own philosophical propensities to support rights. William of Ockham seems to have come to conclusions about subjective rights in a way not necessarily dependent on his nominalist philosophy, since there is evidence that his non-nominalist contemporaries espoused similar ideas about rights and other nominalists did not.³⁰

²⁶ Papanikolaou, *Mystical as Political*, 114–15.

²⁷ See Brian Tierney, *The Idea of Natural Rights: Studies on Natural Rights, Natural Law, and Church Law, 1150–1625* (Atlanta: Scholars Press, 1997).

²⁸ An assertion of Michel Villey, to which Tierney is responding.

²⁹ Papanikolaou, *Mystical as Political*, 115, quoting John McGuckin, *The Ascent of Christian Law*; Nicholas Wolterstorff, "Modern Protestant Developments in Human Rights," in *Christianity and Human Rights*, 155–72.

³⁰ See Tierney, *Idea of Natural Rights*, 97–103.

It is clear that even the paltriest of bases, a mere turn of phrase, can be used to justify rights. The Universal Declaration on Human Rights begins with the statement that “recognition of the inherent dignity and of the equal and inalienable rights of all members of the human family is the foundation of freedom, justice and peace in the world.”³¹ It nowhere explains why such dignity is inherent to humans, nor does it need to explain. It assumes that the reader supplies the fuller justification.

Rights language is quite a bit simpler than Orthodox and other Christian scholars have maintained. That rights do not necessarily cohere to any particular philosophical account does not mean that they are fundamentally a tool of materialists; it means that rights language is a way of speaking, a linguistic technology for expressing a moral and/or legal formulation. To describe a just relationship in terms of what someone is entitled to in a relationship says nothing about *why* a person has that right. Even to say that a person has a right to something by reason of some quality she holds does not constrain us to a particular quality. We need not posit a sharp bifurcation between nature and grace, or even a belief in natural law as it has been articulated in Western Catholic thought. We need not espouse Deism, or a belief in a social contract, or construe justice as the greatest good for the greatest number. We must only answer the question, “On what basis does this being deserve to be treated a certain way?” How a person answers this question will dictate the kind of rights he recognizes.³²

It is true that the modern liberal rights project draws on a worldview that is antithetical to the Orthodox tradition, but that should not lead us inexorably to withdraw from Western political discourse. Clearly, we need our own more compelling reasons for engaging the language of rights. We should expect

³¹ Universal Declaration on Human Rights, preamble.

³² This is why, in Wolterstorff’s view, rights have acquired a bad name: “imagine a society inhabited by possessive individualists. What will they do? Each will claim his own rights while neglecting or refusing to honor the rights of others. In no way does this alter the structure of the rights themselves; that structure remains intact and symmetrical.” *Justice*, 7.

that the rights we advance will be as significantly unique from modern liberal rights as are the worldviews that divide us.

But why, if rights language is so easily manipulated by the forces of secularism, ought we even to consider engaging them? Do we not condemn ourselves to a “faithless future” as Guroian predicts, an ever-encroaching syncretism leading to our collapse? Surely this is ascribing too much power to rights. Modern rights declarations can only ever be, as Yannoulatos says, “a starting point.” Rights “do not safeguard human dignity from becoming enslaved to human egotism, which is the cruelest of all the powers that must be abolished.”³³ This is certainly true, and it is a point that has been brought out in similar fashion by every Orthodox commentator (to my knowledge) on the concept of rights.

But without ascribing too much power to rights, we ought not also to demand more from rights language than it can deliver. Rights are legal expressions enacted through legislation. How could we expect them to safeguard human dignity unless they are enforced? How can rights compete with the call to be truly human? They cannot, but that is asking too much of them. Modern liberalism places rights at the center of its ethical life, but there is nothing about *rights per se* that demands that Orthodoxy ascribe to them the same importance. We are free to justify *and* value rights however we choose.

Rights do exactly what they are intended to do when they are properly employed. They do not do anything to a lesser degree than what they are supposed to do. And rights are only beneficial as long as they remain effective in a culture. They are culturally conditioned, but so are our political theologies. Perhaps what Papanikolaou means by including imperative force in his argument is that liberal democracy currently contains the best resources for expressing Orthodox political theology. But democracy is a political technology, as is the linguistic turn we call rights. Rights are useful not only as long as

³³ Anastasios Yannoulatos, “Orthodoxy and Human Rights: On the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the Greek Orthodox Tradition,” in *Facing the World: Orthodox Christian Essays on Global Concerns* (Crestwood: St. Vladimir’s Press, 2003), 57.

they work in a society, but also only as long as rights are a reasonable way of expressing an Orthodox political theology.

Transfigurational Cosmology

The Christological Cosmology of Maximus the Confessor

The philosophical or theological foundation used to justify rights leads to the expression of certain kinds of rights. The focus of modern Orthodox scholars has been to employ a foundation of theological anthropology to justify human rights. My goal here is to use a broader theological foundation to justify a broader set of potential uses for rights language. The Christological cosmology of Maximus the Confessor, synthesized with the imagery of transfiguration, which I draw from modern patriarchal and hierarchical expositions of environmental theology, will provide the basis for my proposal for how the Orthodox can use rights language.

In *Ambiguum* 7, Maximus provides the building blocks for his Christological cosmology. All created things begin in the motion from non-being to being, a motion that they cannot begin on their own. They must rely on God not just for the genesis of their being but for continuing to be. All created things are not just moving randomly, but moving with definite and constant purpose toward an ultimate end. This end must be, for Maximus, completely impassible, immoveable, uncreated. Nothing that comes into being lacks this end because nothing is self-caused. No created thing is complete; every created thing is a work in progress. This is not to say that the purpose of things changes over time; it is quite to the contrary. Since all things exist by the will of the Creator, they are continually molded by this unerring purpose: “The movement that is tending toward its proper end is called a natural power, or passion, or movement passing from one thing to another and having impassibility as its end.”³⁴ This end is a continual movement and is the *raison d’etre* of all things. Using Scrip-

³⁴ Maximus the Confessor, *Ambig.* 7, quoted from *On the Cosmic Mystery of Christ: St. Maximus the Confessor*, (Crestwood: St. Vladimir’s Press, 2003), 48.

ture, Maximus shows that no creature has ever achieved its end: “no creature has ever ceased using the inherent power that directs it towards its end, nor has it ceased the natural activity that impels it towards its end, nor harvested what it had anticipated.”³⁵ So, this latent purpose is manifested in all things not as a component of being, but as the condition of being by which the will of God calls all things towards Him.

The principle by which Maximus unites the pre-existent intention of God and the purposive movement of each created thing is one he borrows from Dionysius the Areopagite, that the “one Logos is many *logoi*.”³⁶ That each created thing is wholly unique and bears a distinct identity is evidence for Maximus of the presence of God’s *logoi* in all things: “For all things, in that they came to be from God, participate proportionally in God.”³⁷ The *logoi*, then, are “portions of God”; they are truly the Logos of God, which exists and existed in God from before the creation of the world.

The task of all rational beings, then, is the gradual but ultimately perfect out-passing of our self-determination to God. That is, we will gradually hand over our desire for anything else to God, until as saints we have come to a perfect but voluntary desire for God alone. This Maximus calls *ekchōrēsis gnōmikē*, the gnostic handing-over. This is an expression of divinization or *theosis*, and it is the expression of that purposive movement essential to all created things that is given as a particular task of humanity. In other words, the end of humanity fits within the larger purpose of all creation, to be infused with God’s energy in a way that is appropriate to each created thing.³⁸

The nature of humanity’s movement from non-being to being, which can be accomplished only by the impassible and immovable God, is comparable to our movement from being to well-being. When we pursue our beginning, which was our coming-into-being, we are actually pursuing our ultimate end in eternal well-being, which is a gracious gift from God, divi-

³⁵ Ibid., 50.

³⁶ Maximus, *Ambig. 7*, in *On the Cosmic Mystery*, 54.

³⁷ Maximus, *Ambig. 7*, in *On the Cosmic Mystery*, 55.

³⁸ Maximus, *Ambig. 7*, in *On the Cosmic Mystery*, 53.

nization. When we abandon this pursuit, we “slip down from above” and start falling toward non-being. Any such person “enters a condition of unstable gyrations and fearful disorder of soul and body, and though his end remains in place, he brings about his own defection by deliberately turning to what is worse.”³⁹ This characterization of transgression of God’s purpose as instability and violent motion holds an important correspondence with the ecological rhetoric of modern Orthodox patriarchs and hierarchs, which will be addressed below.

The creation of the world and the Incarnation are seamlessly contained in the pre-existent intention of God. Humanity was brought from non-being into being in order to participate in the divine life; this is the mystery of Christ, who is the Logos. This is not a created logos, or world-soul, like the Stoics, but the uncreated Word of God, who in the Incarnation has revealed the fullness of Wisdom. This means that the fabric of the cosmos is knit together with the ultimate divine purpose which is the mystery of Christ:

For it was truly necessary that He who is by nature the Creator of the essence of beings should become in Himself, by grace, the Author of the deification of those whom He created; in order for the Giver of being to appear also as gracious Giver of eternal well-being.⁴⁰

The important thing to note is that eternal well-being is not something from which irrational beings are excluded in Maximus’ eschatological being. Through the Incarnation, our vocation as humans is revealed, one that involves our movement toward eternal well-being. But through restoration and retrieval of this logical purpose, we realize the divine purpose for all creation through Christ. The task of defining humanity’s nature and role in the world and the common destiny of

³⁹ Maximus, *Ambig.* 7, in *On the Cosmic Mystery*, 61.

⁴⁰ Maximus the Confessor, *Ad Thal.* 60, PG 90: 624d; CCSG 22: 79.117 ff. Quoted in Tollefsen, “Logos, Logoi, Created Beings,” *The Christocentric Cosmology of Maximus the Confessor* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2008), 66.

humanity and creation has been undertaken most effectively in the environmental theology of Patriarch Bartholomew and other Orthodox patriarchs and hierarchs.

The Environmental Theology of Transfiguration

Human Nature and Role in Creation

The conception of human nature as composite, as somehow a proper union of the created with the uncreated, is a foundational principle in Orthodox theological anthropology. Gregory the Theologian describes humans as creatures with both human and divine natures:

a great cosmos in miniature; another angel, a “hybrid” worshipper, a full initiate (or: overseer) of the visible creation and initiated also into the intelligible creation; a king of things on earth, but subject to the King above.... A creature trained here and *en route* to somewhere else and – the ultimate mystery – deified by its tendency towards God (Hom. 38 *On Theophany*, 11).⁴¹

We are creatures on the border between creation and the divine, and written into our very existence is our destiny to draw all creation with us toward God. This creates a dual obligation for humanity. We must as proper to our existence participate in the life of the Trinity, which creates an obligation to each other as fellow heirs of the promise. But there is also present to us an obligation to involve all creation in our renewal, making God present to all creation. These two duties are one; we cannot fulfill the one without fulfilling the other.

Elizabeth Theokritoff, in her book *Living in God's Creation*, explains this patristic principle in terms of its implications for how we treat the environment:

Proper use [of creation] is determined *from within* man, by his very makeup. Of course, man is perfectly

⁴¹ Quoted in Theokritoff, *Living in God's Creation: Orthodox Perspectives on Ecology* (Crestwood: St. Vladimir's Seminary Press, 2009), 68–69.

capable of using the earth in a different way – that is all too obvious. But when he does so, he is not simply disobeying a commandment: he is ceasing to be a real human being.⁴²

Human nature as described this way predicates a particular kind of ethical orientation toward the rest of creation, one where humanity's presence in the world is essential. Written into our very being is the need to mediate creation to the Creator. And creation needs us to refer it back to its Creator. This implies that creation *needs* humanity and vice versa. Our priestly role in ecological terms is not just preservation, but "cultivation so that [the world's] ultimate meaning and purpose may be revealed through the human being."⁴³ Basing rights on this vital human-creational relationship generates a different perspective both on how rights ought to be formulated and what rights we seek to secure.

This is a Christocentric vision, but it is Christ related to all creation, so it encompasses the reality of both humanity *and* creation. As humans, we bear the image of God, but Maximus' concept of the *logoi* means that all created things have their own kind of image because they participate in the creative will of God. We are distinct from other creatures, but our common participation in the divine links us together.⁴⁴ As Patriarch Bartholomew said in a 1997 address, "Human beings and the environment form a seamless garment of existence; a complex fabric that we believe is fashioned by God."⁴⁵ The life of God is suffused into creation, and humanity is formed in participation with both God who sustains our life and with creation with which we are knit together.

⁴² Ibid., 69–70.

⁴³ Frederick W. Krueger, ed. *Transfiguring the World: Orthodox Patriarchs and Hierarchs Articulate a Theology of Creation* (Santa Rosa, CA: The Orthodox Fellowship of the Transfiguration, 2008), 98. This last point is important whenever we talk about the goal of our relationship with the environment. Preservation of natural habitats is important, and we certainly should strive toward this as Christians. But if we involve creation in the great saga of our salvation, as God has done, preservation is too static a goal.

⁴⁴ Theokritoff, *Living in God's Creation*, 57–58.

⁴⁵ Krueger, ed. *Transfiguring the World*, 26.

Because we are so bonded, the fall created both an imbalance in our human nature and a disruption of our vocation, which physically and spiritually affected creation. When Adam fell, he stopped living in accordance with his *logos*, his purpose for being. For Adam, that meant his likeness to God, the actualization of his divinization, was lost. This reduced humanity to a state where we could no longer recognize the *Logos* or Wisdom of God in ourselves or in creation, which suffered the effects of this loss. Not only was Adam's nature disrupted, but creation was subjected to futility. When we upset the balance in our own nature, that disharmony resonated in creation.

Not only that, but nature "rebelled" against us, much the same way that a ruler's subjects could be expected to rebel if he has become a tyrant. Symeon the New Theologian explains that when Adam disobeyed God, creation rebelled against Adam in revolt, "no longer wishing to be obedient to the transgressor."⁴⁶ This gives us an image of creation as a victim of the fall, continuing to obey and serve God (as far as we can speak of creation in this personified way) despite Adam's rebellion. Creation's obedience to God in this way takes the form of rebellion against us. This imagery is infused throughout the ecological rhetoric of modern Orthodox leaders. The personification of the creation and a recognition of its status as a victim of the Fall are crucial building blocks in the foundation of transfigurational cosmology.

Eschatology of Transfiguration

Our purpose as human beings is, as Metropolitan Kallistos Ware has said, to "enlarge the radiance of the transfigured Christ."⁴⁷ In the transfiguration of Christ, we are shown that the material world is capable of being illumined by the glory of God. There is a spiritual latency, a divine potentiality in all of creation. And as Patriarch Ignatius IV of Antioch has said, Christ's Incarnation has brought about "the potential trans-

⁴⁶ Symeon the New Theologian, *First Ethical Discourse 2*, quoted in Theokritoff, *Living in God's Creation*, 85.

⁴⁷ Krueger, *Transfiguring the World*, 105–06.

figuration of the universe.... In Him, fallen matter ... rediscovers its vocation in transparency.”⁴⁸ Our task as the image of God is to reveal Creation for what it has always been designed as: a revelation of God. The path from our fallen state towards redemption is a trajectory established in the fabric of the cosmos and in the reality of human nature, given progress and energy by the Spirit of Christ in the lives of saints who are fulfilling their particular vocation in transparency.

This is also an eschatological vision of a transformation of the world, not of its destruction. Methodius of Olympus observes that just as God will not discard our bodies in the resurrection, he will not discard His creation either. Heaven and earth will only “pass away” (Mt. 24.35) in the sense that they will be glorified.⁴⁹ All creation has a value that is defined by its ultimate restoration. That is, it has an eternal value that is eschatologically oriented. The Kingdom of God is a future reality, but is paradoxically the *original*, the manifestation of the mystery of Christ made real in the Eschaton.⁵⁰

This is important because the institution of a measure of worth or value is a component of the philosophical underpinnings needed to generate a robust exercise of rights language. In other words, our answer to the question, “Why does this being deserve to be treated so?” must include some evaluation of that being’s worth. The worth of all created things, including humanity, is an identity that is conditioned eschatologically, one that the Spirit of Christ is calling all of us into from the Eschaton.

This expression of value is based not on some inherent, static quality of humans (e.g., that we are a good creation, or that we are loved by God), but on a trajectory for human flourishing. Our worth is found in our destiny. Papanikolaou finds his argument in the same kind of value. But since he is arguing for the value of *human* rights specifically, he uses

⁴⁸ Ibid., 55.

⁴⁹ Theokritoff, *Living in God’s Creation*, 37.

⁵⁰ This vision competes with those who characterize Orthodoxy as having an entirely futuristic eschatology with no regard for the present reality (e.g., Pollis). It establishes positive regard for the material needs of humanity and the natural world.

theosis as the measure of worth. There is nothing in my own argument here to undermine his argument. The difference is merely one of scope. I am simply advocating for a broader theological field by which worth could be measured and thereby generating a different range of potential rights.

The Transfiguration of Rights

Earlier, I made three assertions about the nature of rights that go against most other Orthodox commentators. I would like to reiterate them here within the framework of the cosmology outlined above. First of all, we do not need nor can we demand of rights that they contain within them the end of human flourishing. We must ask only what rights can supply, which in the case of this cosmology is to remove impediments and establish a trajectory toward that end. In fact, I am asserting that we *must* have in view such an end when employing rights or rights language serves us no purpose as Orthodox Christians. Secondly, rights language is culturally conditioned. The rights we adduce from this cosmology are provisional not because the cosmology is provisional, but because the rights language is. Accomplishing what is equivalent to the right against enslavement without using the language and consequent enforcement of a right against enslavement may at some future point become the most efficient and effective way to express the Orthodox political theology that arises from this cosmology. That makes rights language provisional. Lastly, I address the issue of foregoing one's rights in the pursuit of love or the divine life, however it is stated. Nicholas Wolterstorff has pointed out that the condition of forgiving someone when wronged does not negate a right.⁵¹ For example, if I have a right against enslavement and a person enslaves me, I do not lose my right to freedom by forgiving the one who has enslaved me. Indeed, the wrong done to me and thus the condition under which I forgive my perpetrator is the right I hold to freedom. The focus of those Orthodox scholars who have addressed the relationship between rights and forgiveness has

⁵¹ Wolterstorff, *Justice*, 97–102.

been on the self-sacrifice of the saint in giving up his or her rights in order to forgive or to pursue the higher life. What we have missed is the wrong done by the violator of the saint's rights, whose guilt causes him or her to abandon the divine purpose within. To forgive is the task of the saint, to repent is the task of the perpetrator. If we ignore rights or what they exhibit, we risk ignoring the moral task of the oppressor. The transfigurational cosmology does not allow such a disregard of one of the actors in an ethical situation, but sees the guilty party and the victim as inseparably connected.

Because the transfigurational cosmology establishes the worth of *all creation* and not just humanity, the scope of rights language extends not just to encompass potentially new human rights, but also extends to the protection of non-human creatures and even the environment. If our trajectory toward the divine is contingent on revealing the glory of God within creation, there must be a sense that the rest of creation must also have a kind of right to *be transfigured*.

This opens up possibilities for creating new human, animal, and environmental rights that are inextricably connected in the Orthodox mind. When a man pollutes a stream of water, he has become the perpetrator of a crime against any other person who would benefit from this stream. He has created a disharmony in the world, which effects all creation, human and non-human alike. He has also created of the stream a victim, one which is able to make a claim against the man only to God. Rights established by an Orthodox cosmology must move past the anthropocentric rights articulation that protects only humankind and embrace a more comprehensive view of who (or what) has been wronged and who the perpetrator is.

Again, the objection to the use of rights is that the saint has no need of rights. He does not need to sort out who the perpetrator of a crime is or who has been wronged, since he strives for a sinless life and makes forgiveness his daily habit. But just as rights cannot do what they were not designed to do (have an end), they also do not protect those who have no need of them. Rights do not protect the saints: they protect sinners from other sinners. What we can hope for when we infuse rights with the truth of Orthodoxy is that sinners will be freed from such du-

ress so that the healing of the Holy Spirit might be made more available. That sinner still needs to repent, but he is no longer sinned against, and it is the truth of the Gospel employing the tool of rights language that has lifted this oppressive yoke from his shoulders.

Can rights become empty and lifeless documents, gathering dust in a legal archive? It is possible. That rights require maintenance, moreover, that *good* rights (just like any good law) require good people to demand that they are enforced, is *good* news. Rights can be a permanent connection by which Orthodoxy interacts with the world, but only if Orthodoxy decides to interact with the world consistently. Such rights as are generated from the force of Orthodox theology can only be maintained properly by Orthodoxy. That, again, is good news for Orthodoxy and for the world.

A Practical Rights Proposal

So, what sort of rights are important to produce from this cosmology? Where has the current rights debate suffered from the lack of an application of Orthodox political theology? The rights derived from a transfigurational cosmology are different from those derived from the contractarian vision that characterized this country's Constitution and Bill of Rights.

The rights to freedom of speech or the press are important, but not so foundational as securing the basic right to life or the right against enslavement.

To enact these rights is to secure eschatological trajectories for human flourishing, to recognize and protect the divine purpose and give every human being the opportunity to pursue God. In a way, there is a reciprocal right for the one whose duty it is to protect another's right. Every human has a right against enslavement, but each human also has the right against enslaving. To enslave is to deny oneself the right of pursuing one's divine purpose, which does not include oppressiveness.

Our own belief in the value of life in all its forms has led many Orthodox Christians in America to oppose the taking of the lives of the unborn, but we have also historically recognized the right to mere survival of the living, especially the

right of the poor to the necessary means for survival. John Chrysostom recognized this as a right of the poor to the excess of wealth possessed by the rich; this belongs to the poor for the purpose of their survival. The rich, for their part, must remember the *telos* of their own life, and work against the danger of their own greed condemning them.⁵² Of course, capitalism sometimes encourages and even celebrates greed as a virtue to drive the machine of capitalism. Certainly, then, it would be difficult to justify this right by appealing to the ultimate purpose of a rich person in public discourse. But we may work in the Church to compel such wealthy members of our own society to remember the right of the poor to survival as both a responsibility to their fellow human beings and as fulfilling a particular purpose of their own existence.⁵³ We may even fight to secure those fundamental conditions by which the survival of each individual is rendered more secure, among which are lack of exposure to the elements or daily sustenance to stave off death by starvation or sickness. Even in this case, we may be driven by our own firm belief in the right of the poor to these things without needing recognition of this particular right in American law.

Perhaps the most neglected right that has been recognized both in the United States and internationally is the right against enslavement. Millions now suffer in slavery of various kinds, whether sex slavery through prostitution or pornography, or by economic and political oppression. Slavery is an abnegation of the divine purpose inherent in each human being and a violation of the image of God present in all of us. The present disparity between the ubiquitousness of the slave trade and the nearly universal affirmation of the right against enslavement in the international community is evidence of how important it is to fight for a right. Simply pronouncing that someone has a right to something is no guarantee of any individual's ability to secure that right.

These are two examples of the transfigurational cosmology as applied to human rights, but where it extends beyond human

⁵² See John Chrysostom's *On Wealth and Poverty* 7.

⁵³ In a sense, perhaps the rich have a right to be generous granted through God by virtue of their wealth.

rights, the cosmology generates new and more generous articulations of rights for animals and for the environment. We can establish these rights via the relationship that humans have to animals and the environment, but it is also important to establish them for the value that animals and the natural world have in themselves. The human right to clean air, water, and soil is not a new idea. It has been in the public consciousness in the West for many decades.⁵⁴ To advocate for a right against pollution is to establish a trajectory for the relationship that humans have to their own environment. It identifies the victims of environmental degradation caused by human activity and enjoins action against the perpetrators of pollution. But a right to clean air, water, and soil is discernible via this cosmology even without the human element. In other words, even though the natural world's restoration is contingent on humanity's vocation, the value of the natural world is established not necessarily from humanity's vocation but from its common constitution by means of the eschatological drive, the *logoi* present in all things.

It is important to note the malleability of this cosmology in generating this sort of right, since in the realm of rights, it seems often to have been the case that human rights are fashioned in order to deny or diminish the importance of animal or environmental rights. Arguments in favor of drilling in the Alaskan National Wildlife Refuge, for example, have emphasized the fact that the area is so remote, no humans are able to enjoy it. Putting aside the fact that the goods that might be secured by drilling for oil in the ANWR do not equal a right to those goods, the short-sightedness of this argument is evident in the complete lack of valuation given to the land and the creatures that currently live there. Valuing animals, air, water, land, nature itself, is possible and necessary with an Orthodox political theology built on the transfigurational cosmology.

⁵⁴ Note for example that four U.S. States (Pennsylvania, Illinois, Montana, and Hawaii) have these rights written into their constitutions.

Conclusion

My hope is that this study will fit into a new approach to Orthodox political theology exemplified best by Aristotle Papanikolaou's new book. Though my own way of marshaling the resources of Orthodox theology leads me to slightly different conclusions about the nature of rights and the way they ought to be employed, I value Papanikolaou and other Orthodox scholars' efforts to wrestle with this important issue.⁵⁵ The conversation has suffered in the past from a kind of xenophobia of the West, but the door appears to be opening for a genuine dialogue about how Orthodoxy should behave politically.

We have been cautious of the social artifacts of Western politics because we think they are inevitably tainted. This is surprising, since the Orthodox Church has been so ready in the past to appropriate other artifacts of pagan culture in order to subvert that culture. Even if rights language were not the relatively benign instrument I have asserted that they are, they certainly ought not to represent a threat to the mission of Orthodoxy in the world. What I believe they do represent is the kind of instrument that can serve as a point of connection between the Church and the world. Even though the world's way of doing things is flawed, there exists this admittedly flawed device that is a kind of translator for the energy of Orthodoxy. A simple literary device, elegant in its design, can be infused with theological meaning in such a way that the Church's mission is advanced in the world.

Orthodox political theology has a long way to go. Comprehensive treatments like Papanikolaou's are important, but the dialogue needs to continue. There is still room to augment theological justifications for rights. I have offered a different possibility for grounding rights in Orthodox cosmology, but I certainly do not think it is the only basis possible. To ground

⁵⁵ I cannot conclude this article without acknowledging the excellent political theology offered last year by Pantelis Kalaitzidis, who addresses many of the reasons that the Orthodox have traditionally failed to enter the political arena. It is a valuable critique and exhortation for political engagement: Pantelis Kalaitzidis, *Orthodoxy & Political Theology* (Geneva: WCC, 2012).

human rights in the idea of *theosis* is equally valuable and should be pursued along with other facets of Orthodox theology.

This should lead us to positive, concrete political action. I have given just a few examples of the kind of rights that could be generated from my own theological inquiry, but new ideas should follow. What I did not address at length in this article is the way a local parish might formulate and defend rights in its own community to protect the needs of the poor and oppressed. Of interest too would be the ways in which the Orthodox as a political body might take concrete action in American politics. Clearly, the theology and accompanying ethics of an Orthodox political theology adequate enough to interface with Western political thought is desperately needed and underdeveloped.

Резюме

Опираючись на нове православне політичне богослов'я, зокрема Аристотеля Папаніколау і Пантеліса Калайцідіса, автор статті розпочинає діалог між сучасною теорією прав людини та православним богослов'ям, намагаючись обійти "своєрідну ксенофобію Заходу", що унеможливила попередні спроби почати такий діалог. Цей підхід не є ні некритичною відмовою, ані легковажним прийняттям правової мови, а радше обережним розпізнанням того, які аспекти практики та теорії прав людини є сумісними з православним богослов'ям. Автор широко використовує цю теорію права, виводячи її з допомогою Максима Ісповідника поза соціально-політичну категорію та долучаючи екологічні питання в космологічному контексті. Наприкінці автор закликає до подальшого діалогу, щоби ще краще показати, що права людини не становлять загрози місії Православ'я в світі, а є точкою поєднання між Церквою і світом.